

Documentation of the Review Protocol Evaluation

1. Purpose

This document describes the external evaluation of the review protocol used in the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) entitled 'A Systematic Literature Review of Incident Response Management Maturity Models'. The evaluation aimed to ensure methodological rigor, clarity, completeness, and alignment with established SLR guidelines.

2. Timing of the Evaluation

The protocol was evaluated prior to executing database searches and data extraction. All feedback was incorporated before Stage 2 (Conducting the SLR).

3. Evaluators

Three independent specialists participated:

- 1 Senior academic researcher in cybersecurity and incident response.
- 2 Academic researcher experienced in evidence-based SLR methods.
- 3 Industry CSIRT leader.

4. Evaluation Criteria

The protocol was evaluated regarding:

- 1 Research question clarity and relevance.
- 2 Search strategy completeness.
- 3 Inclusion and exclusion criteria adequacy.
- 4 Quality assessment instrument soundness.
- 5 Reproducibility and transparency.

5. Improvements Implemented

- 1 Added QA indicator for datasets/artifacts.
- 2 Added peer verification in data extraction.
- 3 Minor wording refinements in RQs.

6. Outcome

After these improvements, the protocol was considered suitable for rigorous and reproducible application.

7. Availability

The finalized protocol and this documentation are referenced in the manuscript Data Availability section.